

Study of Chemical Oscillation in a Mixed Substrate System of Gallic Acid and Acetone using Cerium(IV) Ions as Catalyst and a Comparative Study of the Catalytic Activity of Cerium(IV) Ions and Ferroin

S. C. PAL and R. S. BANERJEE*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

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Chemical oscillation has been studied using gallic acid and varying amounts of acetone as the mixed organic substrate both visually and potentiometrically side by side by the batch method. Ce^{IV} ions have been used as catalyst and sulphuric acid as the medium. The results have been compared with those obtained earlier in perchloric acid and sulphuric acid media using ferroin as catalyst. Studies have also been made to judge the relative efficiency of ferroin and Ce^{IV} ions as catalyst with single and mixed organic substrate.

Belousov-Zhabotinskii oscillating reaction¹ is one of the most studied reactions which show oscillatory behaviour. A large number of substances, both organic and inorganic, have been used either as a single substrate or a mixed one. Gallic acid² has been favoured by many workers as the colour changes are very sharp and can be demonstrated easily.

Generally acetone has been used as one of the constituents of mixed organic substrates³. As acetone alone can act both as a bromine scavenger and a reductant, attempts have been made by different workers to see whether it can be used alone. At lower temperature the rate of oxidation of acetone is slow. Hence the system does not oscillate and an additional organic or inorganic reductant is necessary⁴. By increasing the temperature, the rate of oxidation can be enhanced and it is expected that under such conditions the system may oscillate. Rastogi and Misra⁴ observed such oscillation at 50°. Oscillation has also been observed at 31° by other workers⁵ in phosphoric acid medium using ferroin as catalyst presumably thus changing the rate on changing the environment.

In the present study gallic acid and acetone in varying

amounts have been chosen as the mixed organic substrate; Ce^{IV} ions and sulphuric acid have been used as catalyst and medium respectively. Excellent oscillations have been observed. The experimental observations have been compared with those made earlier in perchloric acid⁶ and sulphuric acid⁷ media using the commonest catalyst ferroin. Attempts have also been made to judge whether ferroin or Ce^{IV} ions should be regarded as a better catalyst while using gallic acid alone or gallic acid along with acetone as the substrate. Both visual and potentiometric observations have been made simultaneously. The oscillation parameters, i.e., induction period, number of oscillations, total time of oscillation and oscillation period have been recorded under different conditions like varying concentration of acetone and using a single catalyst, ferroin or Ce^{IV} ions or a mixed catalyst.

Results and Discussion

The oscillation parameters are recorded in Table 1. If the present observations are compared with our earlier observations in perchloric acid system⁶ using ferroin as catalyst, it is observed that the induction period decreases

TABLE 1—STUDY OF OSCILLATION IN (ACETONE-GA)- H_2SO_4 - Ce^{IV} - KBrO_3 B-Z SYSTEM

GA = 0.0235 M, KBrO_3 = 0.0666 M, H_2SO_4 = 2.195N, Ce^{IV} = 0.00083 M, Temp. = $28 \pm 1^\circ$

Acetone % (v/v)	Induction period		No. of oscillations		Total time of oscillations (s)		3rd oscillation period (s)		4th oscillation period (s)	
	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.
0	260	264	3	3	290	288	109	108	—	—
5	334	336	5	5	640	644	124	120	135	142
10	245	240	7	7	663	660	85	84	84	84
15	266	264	12	12	1374	1368	84	80	82	84
20	176	176	14*	23	1884	1968	49	48	48	52
25	143	144	14*	51	540	3552	24	24	28	28
30	98	96	20*	60	590	2928	18	14	18	20

*Not detectable any further.

with increasing concentration of acetone in both the systems (although some variations are there in the present system). The number of oscillations increases with increasing acetone concentration in the present system, but in perchloric acid system, although this number increases in presence of acetone, the change is not much. The total time of oscillation increases with increasing acetone concentration (except in presence of 30% acetone) in the present case, but it decreases in case of perchloric acid-ferroin system (except 5% acetone case). The oscillation periods (third and fourth), however, decrease in both cases. The changes in potential are very much pronounced in the present system, especially when acetone concentration is high. The

Fig. 1. Potential oscillation in GA-KBrO₃-Ce⁴⁺-H₂SO₄ system at different concentrations of acetone (v/v) : (a) 0%, (b) 5% and (c) 10%.

potentiometric traces are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The graphs obtained on plotting the oscillation parameters are shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

It is observed that the presence of acetone definitely increases the probability of oscillation in both cases. The reason for some difference in behaviour in the two systems is not clear.

A comparison of the present potentiometric study (using Ce^{IV} ions as catalyst) with our previous visual study⁷

Fig. 2. Potential oscillation in GA-KBrO₃-Ce⁴⁺-H₂SO₄ system at different concentrations of acetone (v/v) : (a) 15%, (b) 20%, (c) 25% and (d) 30%.

(using ferroin as catalyst) shows that all the oscillation parameters above decrease with increasing acetone concentration when ferroin is the catalyst, whereas the induction period and time period of oscillation decrease and number

Fig. 3.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CATALYST (FERROIN AND/OR Ce^{4+} IONS) ON B-Z SYSTEM CONTAINING GALLIC ACID AND/OR ACETONE AS SUBSTRATE
 GA = 0.0235 M, H_2SO_4 = 2.195 N, $KBrO_3$ = 0.0666 M, Acetone = 30% (v/v), Ferroin = 0.835×10^{-4} M, Ce^{4+} = 0.00083 M, Temp = $32 \pm 1^\circ$

Sl. no.#	Substrate	Catalyst	Induction period (s)		No. of oscillation		Total time of oscillations (s)		3rd. oscillation period (s)		4th oscillation	
			Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vos.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.
1 ^a .	GA	—	290	288	2	2	407	408	196	192	—	—
									(2nd O. P.)	(2nd O. P.)		
2 ^b .	GA	Ferroin	120	96	51	Large no. (>50)	2160	>2016	38	36	39	40
3 ^c .	GA	Ce^{4+}	260	264	3	3	290	288	109	108	—	—
4 ^d .	30% acetone	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
5 ^d .	30% acetone	Ferroin	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
6 ^d .	30% acetone	Ce^{4+}	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
7 ^d .	GA + 30% acetone	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
8 ^e .	GA + 30% acetone	Ferroin	69	72	—	4	—	32	—	8	—	8
9 ^f .	GA + 30% acetone	Ce^{4+}	60	60	detection difficult	60	—	2220	—	10	—	12
10 ^g .	GA + 30% acetone	Ferroin + Ce^{4+}	58	56	7	7	87	88	10	11	13	12

* Remarks : ^aVide Fig. 5(a); visible also. ^bVide (Fig. 5(b)); visible also; complex oscillation towards the end. ^cTemp. 29°; vide Fig. 1(a); visible also; after cessation of oscillation, addition of ferroin leads to some irregular oscillations, ^dNo oscillation. ^eVide Fig. 5(c); only a few quick oscillations. Addition of Ce^{4+} later leads to further small pot, oscillation (visible also). ^fVide Fig. 6(a); very good oscillation; after cessation of oscillations addition of ferroin leads to further good oscillations. ^gVide Fig. 6(b); several quick oscillations; visible also.

of oscillations and total time of oscillation increase with Ce^{IV} ions as catalyst. This anomalous behaviour remains unexplained. The decrease in induction period and time period with increase in acetone concentration, can, however, be rationalised⁵ by the fact that an increase in con-

centration of acetone increases both the rates of removal of bromine as well as the reduction of oxidized metal species.

The effect of the catalyst, ferroin and/or Ce^{IV} ions is shown in Table 2 and the potentiometric traces are presented in Figs. 5 and 6. It is observed that although the presence of acetone increases the probability of oscillation, acetone alone does not show oscillation in absence or presence of ferroin or Ce^{IV} ions under the present conditions. When gallic acid is the only substrate present, it shows a few oscillations in the absence of a catalyst, also a few oscillations in presence of Ce^{IV} ions, but a large number of oscillations in presence of ferroin. But strangely enough, when gallic acid and acetone are used together, no oscillation takes place in the absence of a catalyst. So it appears that in the uncatalysed case, acetone suppresses the oscillation.

Further, when both gallic acid and acetone are present, only a few quick oscillations take place in presence of ferroin, whereas a large number of oscillations is observed in presence of Ce^{IV} ions and the potential changes are

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5. Potential oscillation in GA and/or acetone-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄ system : (a) GA, no catalyst, (b) GA, ferriin and (c) GA, 30% acetone, ferriin.

Fig. 6. Potential oscillation in GA-acetone-KBrO₃-H₂SO₄ system : (a) GA, 30% acetone, Ce^{IV}, (b) GA, 30% acetone, ferriin, Ce^{IV}.

higher. When ferriin is the catalyst, a later addition of Ce^{IV} ions after cessation of oscillation in presence of ferriin alone, leads to further small potential oscillations which

are visible also. On the other hand, when Ce^{IV} ions are used as catalyst, fresh excellent oscillations start on addition of ferriin after the cessation of initial very good oscillations. Thus Ce^{IV} ion is not a good catalyst and much less efficient than ferriin when gallic acid alone is the substrate; but it acts as a very good catalyst in a mixed substrate system containing gallic acid and acetone. It is also noted that when both the catalysts are present in the mixed substrate system, several very quick oscillations take place and these are visible also.

The FKN mechanism⁸ for metal ion catalysed Belousov reactions and OKN mechanism⁹ for uncatalysed systems have been fruitfully used to elucidate the main aspects of these reactions. In the present case, it is likely that the reaction involves the oxidation of gallic acid by KBrO₃ to its quinonoid form¹⁰ (Q) which is converted to quinone radical by Br[•] or BrO₂[•] and ultimately bromogallic acid is formed,

In presence of ferriin catalyst or Ce^{IV} ions, the usual reactions take place, and in absence of external catalyst, the quinonoid form (Q) acts as the effective catalyst. The observation that the number of oscillations is much less in uncatalysed case is probably due to the fact that ferriin or Ce^{IV} ion helps the system to cross a threshold barrier quickly whereas Q is less efficient in this respect.

Experimental

To a weighed amount of gallic acid, requisite amounts of acetone, water and a solution of ceric sulphate in sulphuric acid were added and the reaction was triggered by addition of potassium bromate solution. All the solutions were so prepared and mixed that the concentrations shown in Tables 1 and 2 are the concentrations in medium at the start. For obtaining data in Table 2, gallic acid and/or acetone solution were used as the mixed or single organic substrate and ceric sulphate solution and/or ferriin solution used as mixed or single catalyst. Nothing was added during the run of the reaction so as to obtain a closed system in the thermodynamic sense. The reaction mixture was moderately stirred at a fixed rate. The oscillations were recorded visually from the sharp colour changes, deep brown to golden yellow when Ce^{IV} ions were the catalysts and red to blue when ferriin was the catalyst. For potentiometric measurement, a bright platinum electrode was

used in the reaction vessel which was connected to a saturated calomel electrode (reference electrode) through an ammonium nitrate salt-bridge. The potential of the system was recorded with the help of a *X-t* strip chart recorder. After cessation of oscillation with a catalyst, the other catalyst was added to see whether further oscillations took place. This helped to judge the efficiency of the catalysts.

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